

Synthesis of Some Novel Monocyclic beta-Lactam Derivatives

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Syntheses of several novel monocyclic β -lactam derivatives have been reported. These compounds possess all the characteristics of the classical β -lactam antibiotics and are suitable for elaboration to polyheterocyclic derivatives.

A number of monocyclic β -lactam derivatives display interesting physiological properties^{1,2}. Bose and coworkers³ have synthesised some monocyclic β -lactam derivatives that elicit good antimicrobial properties. Recently nocardicin^{4,5} has added new impetus on the investigation of monocyclic β -lactams. The search for newer such derivatives led to the synthesis of a number of monocyclic β -lactam derivatives possessing the features of classical β -lactam antibiotics. These are presented here. All the compounds synthesised possess a *cis* stereochemistry, a high β -lactam carbonyl stretching frequency and a suitably disposed ester functionality which could be hydrolysed *in vivo* or *in vitro*.

2-Naphthaldehyde (1) and 9-phenanthraldehyde (4) were reacted with various amino ester hydrochlorides, synthesised from readily available amino acids, in benzene and in presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate to afford the desired imines in excellent yield. These imines, in general, are crystalline solids and were characterised by their spectroscopic data (Table 1) and elemental analysis.

The β -lactams were synthesised by the addition of the appropriate acid chlorides to a well stirred solution of the imines⁶ (Scheme 1). All these new β -lactams were identified by their spectroscopic data (Table 2) and elemental analysis, and they exhibit a high infrared carbonyl absorption frequency. The coupling constant of the two hydrogen atoms attached to the β -lactam ring indicate clearly that the stereochemistry was *cis* (J 5 to 7 Hz) in every case.

β -Lactams (6b and 6d) were reduced with hydrogen sulphide-triethylamine in dichloromethane to afford the amines (7b and 7d), which was reacted with benzoyl chloride to give the amides (8b and 8d). The amine and the amide were characterised by usual physical methods.

We have also synthesised a number of β -lactams of types 11 and 14 (Scheme 2).

All the imines were obtained in very good yield and are quite stable. The crowded *ortho*-substituted-imines (13b and 13c) required prolonged reaction

Scheme 1

time for their formation, which can be attributed to steric as well as electronic factors. The structures of the imines and β -lactams were confirmed by usual physical methods.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries using a Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are

TABLE-1

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ (CHCl ₃) cm ⁻¹	δ (CDCl ₃)	m/e (M ⁺)
2a	115	1660, 1740	3.2 (2H, m), 4.9 (2H, m), 5.3 (1H, m) 7.0-7.8 (18H, m)	393 302 (91) 258 (135)
2b	102	1652, 1730	3.3 (2H, m), 3.75 (3H, s), 4.3 (1H, m) 7.2-8.19 (13H, m)	317 258 (59) 236 (91)
2c	(Oil)	1650, 1745	3.8 (3H, s), 4.2 (2H, s), 7.05-7.85 (8H, m)	227 168 (59)
5a	92	1660, 1743	3.35 (2H, m), 3.8 (3H, s), 4.5 (1H, m), 6.9-8.3 (15H, m)	367 276 (91) 217 (150)
5b	(Oil)	1656, 1740	3.75 (3H, s), 4.6 (2H, s), 7.1-8.2 (10H, m)	277 218 (59)
10a	121	1655, 1738	3.1 (2H, s), 4.4 (1H, m), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.8-8.1 (18H, m)	393 302 (91)
10b	89	1665, 1745	3.2 (2H, s), 3.9 (3H, s), 4.9 (1H, m), 7.0-8.0 (13H, m)	317 258 (59)
10c	(Oil)	1662, 1748		227 168 (59)
13b	109	1640, 1730		347
13c	127	1630, 1735	3.75 (3H, s), 4.05 (3H, s), 4.35 (2H, s), 7.15-8.2 (7H, m)	257

TABLE-2

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ (CHCl ₃ /nujol) cm ⁻¹	δ (CDCl ₃ /DMSO d ₆)	m/e (M ⁺)
3a	145	1780, 1740	3.5 (2H, m), 4.3 (1H, d, J 5Hz), 5.2 (3H, m), 5.5 (1H, d), 7.15-7.8 (22H, m)	527
3b	132	1785, 1750	3.0 (2H, m), 3.6 (3H, s), 4.4 (1H, m), 4.9 (1H, m), 5.3 (1H, d J 6Hz), 6.9-8.2 (17H, m)	451
3c	115	1780, 1730	3.7 (3H, s), 4.1 (2H, s), 4.5 (1H, d J 5.5Hz), 5.2 (1H, d J 5.5Hz), 6.85-8.2 (12H, m)	361
6a	172	1782, 1750	3.4 (2H, m), 3.6 (3H, s), 4.6 (1H, d J 6Hz), 4.9 (1H, m), 5.4 (1H, d J 6Hz), 6.9-8.5 (19H, m)	501
6b	160	2160, 1785, 1750		450
6c	142	1780, 1745	3.85 (3H, s), 4.6 (2H, s), 5.5 (1H, d J 6Hz), 5.9 (1H, d J 6Hz), 7.0-8.35 (14H, m)	411
6d	133	2100, 1780, 1740	3.9 (3H, s), 4.0 (1H, s), 4.6 (1H, s), 5.25 (1H, d J 5.8Hz), 5.8 (1H, d J 5.8Hz), 7.1-8.2 (9H, m)	360
11a	109	1775, 1745	3.42 (2H, s), 4.65 (1H, d), 4.8 (1H, s), 5.8 (2H, s), 5.5 (1H, d J 6Hz), 6.9-8.1 (22H, m)	527
11b	87	1775, 1740	3.15 (2H, s), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.55 (1H, d J 6Hz), 5.1 (1H, m), 5.95 (1H, d J 5.6Hz), 6.8-8.2 (17H, m)	451
11c	69	1770, 1735	3.60 (3H, s), 4.4 (1H, d J 6Hz), 4.9 (1H, m), 5.2 (1H, d J 6Hz), 6.9-8.2 (12H, m)	361
14b	121	1760, 1725		481
14c	128	1765, 1720	3.8 (3H, s), 4.05 (3H, s), 4.45 (2H, d J 5.5Hz), 5.2 (1H, m), 5.45 (1H, d J 5.6Hz), 6.75-8.1 (12H, m)	391

uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 B grating spectrophotometer. Proton magnetic resonance spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer with TMS as an internal reference. The solvent used for the reactions were of analytical grade and perfectly dried.

The aldehydes were synthesised according to the procedure described in the literature⁷⁻⁹. Some typical experimental procedures are reported below.

L-β-Phenylalanine methyl ester hydrochloride: L-β-Phenylalanine (8.25 g, 0.05 mol) was suspended in methanol (40 ml) and was stirred at 0-5°, and then thionyl chloride (7.0 g, 0.06 mol) was added dropwise and stirring continued for 7 h at 0-5°. The reaction mixture was then kept at 10° for 12 h, and at 40° for another 10 h. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure. It was then cooled and ether was added. The resulting white precipitate was washed repeatedly with ether to remove traces of thionyl chloride. Recrystallisation from ethanol afforded shining white crystals (70%), m.p. 126°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1725 (CO/ester) and 2950 cm⁻¹ (N⁺-H).

L- β -Phnylalanine benzyl ester hydrochloride : *L*- β -phenylalanine (8.25 g, 0.05 mol), thionyl chloride (7.00 g, 0.06 mol) and benzyl alcohol (30 ml) were reacted following the same procedure as described above to yield the product (60%), m.p. 149°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1728 (CO/ester) and 2950 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}^+ - \text{H}$).

Glycine methyl ester hydrochloride : Using glycine (15 g, 0.2 mol), methanol (50 ml) and thionyl chloride (26 g, 0.22 mol) the product was obtained (80%), m.p. 140°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1725 (CO/ester) and 2910 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}^+ - \text{H}$).

Synthesis of imines : To a suspension of the appropriate amine ester hydrochloride (0.02 mol) in benzene, triethylamine (0.025 mol) was added and stirred for 3 h. A solution of the appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) in benzene was then added dropwise followed by a large excess of anhydrous sodium sulphate (15 g), and the whole mass was stirred for 2 h and refluxed for 4 h. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with cold water, dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and removal of solvent *in vacuo* gave the desired imines.

In the case of the imines 13b and 13c, a prolonged refluxing period (10 h) was needed (checked by ir, the absence of aldehyde carbonyl and the presence of strong imine band).

Synthesis of β -lactams : A solution of the freshly prepared imine (0.005 mol) and dry triethylamine (0.505 g, 0.005 mol) in dichloromethane (50 ml) was stirred at -5° under nitrogen atmosphere. To this was added a solution of the acid chloride (0.005 mol) in dichloromethane (15 ml) over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight and poured into ice-water (30 ml). The organic layer was separated, washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, with water, dried over MgSO_4 and evaporated to give a residue which was recrystallised from the appropriate solvents.

4-(9'-Phenanthryl)-1-(α -carbomethoxyphenylethyl)-3-amino-2-azetidione (7b) : To a solution of the azido- β -lactam (6b; 4.50 g, 0.01 mol) in dichloromethane (50 ml) at 0° was added triethylamine (1.2 g, 0.012 mol). A stream of H_2S gas was bubbled in for 0.5 h. The solution was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. A stream of N_2 gas was bubbled in the solution for 0.5 h. The solution was then washed with water, dried and evaporation of the solvent gave the title compound (4.03 g, 96%), m.p. 137° (Found : C, 76.28; H, 5.40; N, 6.39. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ calcd. C, 76.41, H, 5.66; N, 6.60%); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3400 (NH_2), 1782 (CO/lactam) and 1720 cm^{-1} (CO/ester).

4-(9'-Phenanthryl)-1-(α -carbomethoxymethyl)-3-amino-2-azetidione (7d) : The synthesis was carried

out according to the procedure described for 7b, to yield the product (91%), m.p. 118° (Found : C, 71.99, H, 5.42; N, 8.10. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ calcd. C, 71.85; H, 5.68; N, 8.38%); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3450 (NH_2), 1780 (CO/lactam) and 1735 cm^{-1} (CO/ester).

4-(9'-Phenanthryl)-1-(α -carbomethoxyphenylethyl)-3-benzamido-2-azetidione (8b) : To a stirred solution of the amine (7b; 0.42 g, 0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.12 g, 0.001 mol) in dichloromethane (50 ml), was added slowly a solution of benzoyl chloride (0.14 g, 0.001 mol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) and stirred for further 3 h. The solution was then washed with 20 ml of buffer solution (pH 4.5) followed by water, dried and evaporated to give solid material which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether to yield the product (0.33 g, 64%), m.p. 171° (Found : C, 76.93; H, 5.47; N, 4.86. $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ calcd. C, 77.27; H, 5.30; N, 5.30%); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3450 (NH), 1785 (CO/lactam), 1725 (CO/ester), and 1662 cm^{-1} (CO/amide); δ (CDCl_3) 3.4 (2H, m), 3.9 (2H, s), 4.7 (1H, d), 4.9 (1H, m), 5.3 (1H, d) and 7.1-8.35 (20H, m).

4-(9'-Phenanthryl)-1-(α -carbomethoxymethyl)-2-azetidione (8d) : The amidification was performed in a manner analogous to the synthesis of compound 8b to yield the product (72%), m.p. 149° (Found : C, 79.60; H, 5.38; N, 6.63. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ calcd. C, 79.80; H, 5.41; N, 6.89%); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3390 (NH), 1780 (CO/lactam), 1730 (CO/ester) and 1660 cm^{-1} (CO/amide); δ (CDCl_3) 3.75 (3H, s), 4.0 (1H, s), 4.2 (1H, s), 5.1 (1H, d), 5.4 (1H, d) and 7.3-8.3 (15H, m).

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